

Two Tehuelche Folktales

recorded by Ramón Lista in 1877-79

Adapted from:

Ramón Lista: Los indios Tehuelches, una raza que desaparece. Buenos Aires: Coni 1894.

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Los_indios_tehuelches_-_Ramon_Lista.pdf

Translated from Spanish to English

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The Fox and the Stone

Adapted from: p. 53 in the primary source

Narrator: unidentified

Time of recording: between 1877 and 1879

A fox challenged a stone to a race; this one excused itself:

»I'm very heavy.«

»We will run down that hill,« the fox insisted.

»I am very heavy ... but beware of me ...«

»You will catch up with me? What madness! I run like the wind.«

»Alright, let's run,« said the stone.

And the fox left like an arrow ... The stone then began to roll, and from tumble to tumble, he went to mortally wound its rival, who had already reached the foot of the hill.

The Fox and the Puma

Adapted from: p. 54 in the primary source

Narrator: unidentified

Time of recording: between 1877 and 1879

A puma found himself at the edge of a haystack with a very gentle fox.

(It should be noted that this one had a colorful crest on his head.)

»What a beautiful decoration you are wearing, my friend! How did you make it?« spoke the beast.

»Very simply: I scraped my head with a flint, and then I inserted the beautiful rhea feathers into it.«

»How admirable! I wish to submit to the same test. Do you want to go to the trouble of doing it for me?«

»With great pleasure.«

And the fox began to scratch the puma's skull, until he had thinned it enough to break it with a single blow of a flint.

And the puma died.

